

Tracking Number:

Remove X

9505516159786094160229

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Add to Informed Delivery (<https://informedelivery.usps.com/>)

Latest Update

Your item was delivered to an individual at the address at 9:29 am on April 6, 2026 in WASHINGTON, DC 20515.

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USPS Tracking Plus[®]

Delivered

Delivered, Left with Individual

WASHINGTON, DC 20515
April 6, 2026, 9:29 am

Arrived at Post Office

WASHINGTON, DC 20018
April 6, 2026, 7:59 am

Arrived at USPS Regional Destination Facility

WASHINGTON DC DISTRIBUTION CENTER
April 5, 2026, 5:27 pm

Arrived at USPS Regional Origin Facility

QUEENS NY DISTRIBUTION CENTER
April 5, 2026, 12:33 am

Departed Post Office

RIDGEWOOD, NY 11385
April 4, 2026, 3:33 pm

USPS in possession of item

RIDGEWOOD, NY 11385
April 4, 2026, 11:04 am

● **Hide Tracking History**

What Do USPS Tracking Statuses Mean? (<https://faq.usps.com/s/article/Where-is-my-package>)

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USPS Tracking Plus®

Product Information

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Track Another Package

Enter tracking or barcode numbers

Need More Help?

Contact USPS Tracking support for further assistance.

FAQs